

COMMULATIVE PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AS CORRELATES OF FITNESS, HEALTH STATUS AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AMONG STUDENTS

By

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to examine the level of fitness that resides in students as a result of involvement in physical activities and how the accumulated physical activities boost the fitness, health status and above all help improve academic performance of students. Several literatures were consulted as could be seen in the reference page. At the end of the study, it was discovered that participation in physical activities as planned by authorities and professionals helped greatly to improve the fitness level, health status and upon all, provide the bases for better academic achievement among students. On the other side, sedentary life styles and consumption of specific intakes, poor lifestyle behaviour, poor environments (physical and social) as well as poor personal attributes go a long way to promote poor and unacceptable physical fitness, level, poor health status and less attractive academic performances.

Key Words: *Cummulative physical activity, Health Status, Academic Achievements, Fitness level.*

Introduction

In recent years, the performance levels of fundamental motor skills by students have attracted major attention in literature. During the second half of the last century in the area of physical activity and health, two consistent themes emerged among others in the professional literature. The first one was the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services which tends to

provide substantial health benefits; and second, the prevalence of physical activity among adult populations as a major public health concern. Similarly, Walkley, Holland, Rose, Treloar and Prohynsmith (2011), reported that in a statewide research findings, there was high failure rate boys (50%), girls (75%) in reaching a mature form of various fundamental motor skills. Thompson, McCormack, Thomas & Woodock, (2005) and more recently, Booth, Macaskill, Phongsavan, Patterson, Wright, Bauman & Baur, (2007) reinforced these findings, thus suggesting that the poor levels of proficiency in fundamental skills is not a problem only of the White, but is widespread throughout the world.

The world's health is undergoing an unprecedented transition on several fronts, including epidemiological, nutritional and demographic (Cameron, 2009). The result is a broad shift in disease-borne from minor to major prevalence. A report from the World Health Organization (WHO, 2003) predicts that majority of deaths by broad cause (59%) are from non-communicable diseases (NCD) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Death by broad cause group 2000

Source: WHO, World Health Report, 2003

The report further states that in European, American and Western Pacific regions, NCDs are in an overwhelming majority. The South-East Asia and Eastern Mediterranean Regions are in transition, with NCDs now a more significant health problem than infectious diseases. The WHO reports that the African region is also in transition, with communicable diseases still predominant in most countries of the region, but warns that the incidences of NCDs are increasing (WHO, 2003).

Data contained in the World Health Organization (WHO) report (2003) show that high blood pressure is a major contributing factor of all deaths in the world especially in Nigeria. Of the ten leading risk factors, six relate to nutrition, diet and physical activity (Murat' &, Lopez, 2006). The report suggests that progress in these two areas, combined with reductions in tobacco and alcohol use, will have enormous impact on the prevention of NCDs and will lead to major health gains that are cost-effective (WHO, 2003). This suggests that more lives could be saved through modifying inactive behaviour patterns than by modifying any other coronary health disease risk factor (Sallis & Saelens, 2010).

Prevalence of Physical Activities

There are enormous effects associated with an increased prevalence of physical activity, not the least of which is the economic benefits on the individual and community (Pate, Pratt, Bliar, Haskel, Macera, and bouchard, 2005). The World Health Organization report of 2003 highlights that while communicable disease, food shortages and under nutrition are still being encountered in many countries in the African region, like the rest of the world, these countries are also affected by epidemiological, nutritional and demographical transition.

Non-communicable diseases, especially Cardiovascular Disease (CVD) are increasing rapidly throughout the African region and were estimated to

have caused 22% of all deaths in 2001. They now constitute the major health problem in some countries (e.g. Algeria, Mauritius and Seychelles) and are as important a cause of death as communicable diseases in others (e.g. Cote d'Ivoire and Nigeria). In Harare, prevalence in women of the risk factor, obesity, ($BM I = 30\text{kg/m}^2$) is now higher than that of HIV infection (WHO, 2003).

These figures point to the significant role of under nutrition, which should not be overlooked when addressing the challenges of over nutrition, the report states. In many countries, both forms of malnutrition co-exist. Balanced diets are essential for providing population health. However, a surprisingly high prevalence of over weight is found in African countries especially among women. Childhood obesity is also a growing problem across the world, with physical inactivity a major factor (WHO, 2003).

Physical activity is most often defined in the context of energy expenditure as any bodily movement produced by the skeletal muscles that substantially increase energy expenditure over the resting level (Bouchard & Shepherd, 2010). Although physical activity is often evaluated in terms of energy expenditure, it can be seen as bio-cultural behaviour, whereby energy is expended in active behaviours that occur in different forms and cultural contexts (Malina, 2010). Physical fitness, on the other hand, is an adaptive state with a set of attributes that people have or achieve which relates to the ability to perform physical activities with reserve for recreation (Holland, 2006).

Over the past 30 years, a variety of population have been studied for possible relationships between physical activity, body composition, physiological fitness and cardiovascular health. The unique and fundamental contributions of epidemiology have been recognized as a means of understanding the causes of cardiovascular diseases, and as procedures to preventing and controlling them (Berlin and Colditz, 2011, Powell,

Thompson, Casperson and Kendrick, 2011). This according to them leads to the realization that physical activity protects human beings against the development of Coronary Heart Diseases (CHD), stroke, hypertension and obesity (Bouchard and Shepherd, 2010).

The relationship between physical activity, health-related fitness and health in adult population can be examined and understood from a model presented in Figure 2 (Bouchard & Shepherd, 2010). Physical activity may influence fitness which in turn modify the level of physical activity. With increasing fitness, people tend to become more active, and the fittest persons tend to be the most active. The association between fitness and health is also reciprocal. Fitness influences health while health status also influences both physical activity and fitness. There are also other factors that influence physical activity, fitness and health e.g. lifestyle factors other than physical activities, personal attributes, physical environment and social environment (Fig. 2). Lifestyle behaviours for instance, include; smoking, diet, alcohol consumption, sleeping pattern etc. several personal attributes such as age, gender, social-economic status, personality, motivation and attitude towards physical activity and other health habits may shape people's lifestyle or patterns. Social environments combine social, cultural, political and economic conditions that affect physical activity, fitness and health. Environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, air quality, altitude and climatic changes, may influence physical activity, health related fitness and health.

Heredity as Factor:

Heredity has an impact on all the three components of the model, that is, physical activity, fitness and health status. There are heredity differences in the levels of physical activity and in the component of health related fitness. Interaction between the genes and the environment is largely responsible for the variability in the health related genotypes in response to

physical activity. Different genotypes may be at different risks for diseases associated with physical activity and a low level of health related fitness. (Bouchard, 2009). There are marked individual differences in responsiveness to a certain dose of physical activity. Because the result of physical activity intervention studies are usually presented as the average effect of the observed groups, individual responses to the certain training programme may vary.

Fig. 2

Figure 2: A model describing the relationship between physical activity, health-related fitness and health

Source: Adapted from Bouchard and Shepherd, 2010

Furthermore, physical exercise improves functional capacity, enhances mood, thought and psychological behaviour and delays the infirmities and disabilities of old age (Mauna, 2010). The favourable effects of regular physical activity on health are nowadays recognized. The dose-response relationship between physical activity and health varies for different health outcomes (Sallis and Sagens, 2010). The general physical activity recommendation to enhance health suggests 30 minutes of moderate intense physical activity on most days of the week (Pate, Blair, Haskell, Macera and Boushard, 2005). This can be interpreted as a minimal dose of physical activity to guarantee most of the health benefits. However, the prevalence of physically inactive persons is relatively high in most Western countries emphasizing the significance of inactivity as a public hazard (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2006).

Significance of Physical Activities:

Physical activity is inter-related with energy expenditure which may cause elevation of metabolic rate and influence other physical fitness and health attributes of the body (Armstrong and Welshman, 2008). The Centre for Disease Control and the American College of Sports Medicine recommended that children and adults should gradually build up to 30 minutes of activity of moderate intensity, preferably all days of the week (Pate, Pratt, Blair, Haskell, Macera, Bouchard, 2009). Activities of moderate intensity burn 4 - 7 kilocalories per minute (kcal/min) and have metabolic equivalent (MET) value of 3.0 -- 6.0. Examples of moderate physical activities are level walking at 2.5 - 4kph, cycling at 5.5 - 9.7kph. swimming at least and most racket sports (Welk and Morro, 2010). Anyone involved in or who participates in walking more than 3km for at least 5 days a week and other moderate-vigorous physical activities will be classified as being sufficiently active whereas anyone who does any type of moderate-vigorous activity in at

least 1 day and walks less than 3km is only active while sedentary people are those who do less than 1km of walking daily.

Regular physical activity during adolescence is positively associated with skeletal health (Bailey & Martin, 2006), emotional well-being (Shepherd & Lavelle, 2007); academic performance (Shepherd, 2008); and mental health variables such as self-esteem, self-concept, depression, anxiety (Calfas & Taylor, 2009). In addition, regular physical activity during adolescence is inversely associated with obesity (Cameron, 2009); hypertension (Alpert & Wilmone, 2006); hypercholesterolemia (Caig, Bandini, Leichtenstein, Shaefer & Dietz, 2006); marijuana use (Pate et al, 2005); and frequency of cigarette smoking (Murray & Lopez 2006).

A low level of physical activity is known to be associated with an increased rate of all-cause mortality (Lee, 2010), increased incidence of cardiovascular diseases (Kohi, 2011), colon cancer (Thume & Furberg, 2011). Physical inactivity is also associated with an unfavourable profile of cardiovascular risk factors, such as high level of blood pressure (Fagard et al, 2011) and blood lipids (Leon & Sanchez, 2010).

A low level of cardiorespiratory fitness is associated with an increased risk of cardiovascular diseases and mortality, and the least fit 20% of the population is reported to be at special risk compared with moderately (the next 40%) or highly fit groups (the highest 40%) (Bloom, 2007). Physical activity is a means of controlling weight by increased energy expenditure, but obesity may also influence motivation to participate in physical activities. The global estimate for the prevalence of physical activity among adults is 17% according to the World Health Report (WHO, 2003). The report further stated that estimates for prevalence of some, but insufficient activity (<2.5 hours per week of moderate activity) range from 31% to 51%, with a global average of 41% across the sub-regions.

Physical Activities and Academic Achievements:

Majority of studies in various regional survey fail to meet recommended minimum activity standards (Lambert, Bohlmann, and Kolbe-Alexander, 2010). Benefice, Gamier and Ndiaye, (2011) reviewed some physical activity studies done among Nigerian students at higher educational institutions and found them to be good attempts, since most of the studies describing the physical activity patterns among adolescents were done in developed countries. Although not representative, the studies revealed the problem of physical inactivity among adolescents and students in tertiary institutions in Nigeria (Benefice et al, 2011). The authors equally assessed the effect of different levels of regular physical activity on the physical fitness and health status of school children aged 6 - 11 years. A validated Children's Activity Rating Scale (CARS) developed by the authors was used to obtain information about the children's physical activity levels. The findings of the study revealed lack of regular organized physical education programmes. It further indicated that physical activity could be used to improve the body composition and physical fitness of children.

Worldwide, childhood obesity has revealed epidemic proportions with 155 million school aged children being either obese or over weight (Noakes, 2004). The Youth risk Behaviour Survey of 2002 revealed that 17% of adolescents in South Africa are overweight and 4% are obese. With regard to physical activity, 29% had no physical education classes in school and 25% watched Television for over 3 hours per day. This trend is equally reported by Benefice et al, 2011 in their study. According to them, physical activity helps to prevent and treat obesity non-pharmacologically, by increasing the amount of energy expended, and increasing the resting metabolic rate.

Research by (Nielsen &, Andersen: 2003) which investigated the relationship between inactivity and hypertension found that more active and fit subjects exhibited low systolic and diastolic blood pressures. The findings

suggest that active and fit people are at a reduced risk of developing hypertension thereby promoting better academic achievements.

The normal everyday activities in which children participate, including traveling to and from school can contribute to their daily quantum of physical and academic activities which in turn, should lead to healthier lives (Biddle, Cavil and Sallis, 2008). Studies on exercise, physical activity and the prevention of chronic diseases are limited and few data exist which describe the relationship between participation in physical activity and cardiovascular disease risk factors of urban school children. Therefore, determination of physical activity during adolescence provides many proximal and distal benefits to an individual's health and achievement, hence this type of research should be given prominence in this country.

Despite conventional wisdom that school inputs make little difference in student learning, a growing body of research suggests that schools can make a difference, and a substantial portion of that difference is attributable to teacher regular activities. Recent studies of teacher-effects at the classroom level using the Tennessee Value-Added Assessment System and a similar data base in Dallas, Texas, have found that differential teacher-effectiveness is a strong determinant of differences in student learning. This result, far outweighed the effects of differences in class size and heterogeneity (Sallis & Saelens, 2010; Welk & Morrow, 2010; Johnson & Nelson, 2010). Students who are assigned to several ineffective teachers in a row have significantly lower achievement and gains in achievement than those who are assigned to several highly effective teachers in sequence (Welk Morrow, 2010). Teacher-effects appear to be additive and cumulative, and generally not compensatory. These studies also find troubling indicators for educational equity, noting evidence of strong bias in assignment of students to teachers to different effectiveness levels (Johnson & Nelson, 2010), including indications that African American students are nearly to be assigned

to the most effective teachers (Welk & Morrow, 2010). These studies did not, however, examine the characteristics or practices of more and less effective teachers.

Booth (2007) summarized the results of thirty studies relating teachers' physical activity subject matter knowledge to student achievement. The teacher knowledge measures were neither a subject knowledge test (standardized or researcher-constructed) of number of college courses taken within the subject area. The results of these studies were mixed, with 17 showing a positive relationship and 14 showing no relationship. However, many of the "no relationship" studies, the authors noted, had so little variability in the teacher knowledge measure. That insignificant findings were almost inevitable. Berlin and Coldits (2011) found only 15 of 19 studies they reviewed exhibited a positive relationship between measures of academic subject matter knowledge and physical activity performances.

Conclusion

From the findings of literature consulted, there exist revelations that appropriate physical activities goes a long way to promote health of people, brings about good development and excellent performance not only on the field of play but even in the class room work and in all academic tasks. Therefore, the need for all stakeholders to gear effort up at making sure that the performance of planned physical activities should be for almost especially from the younger ones through to the adults. While planning these activities, relevant factors such as needs, interests, availabilities, background and economic power of the stakeholders and standardization of facilities should be considered.

Bouchard, C. and Shephard, R. J. (2010). Physical Activity, Fitness, and Health: The Model and key Concepts. In: Bouchard C, Shephard, R. J. and Stephens, F. (Eds.) *Physical Activity, Fitness, and Health: International Proceedings and Consensus Statement*. Champaign Illinois: Human Kinetics.

Recommendations

For better academic achievement through physical activities, it is recommended that community and the school should embrace daily physical activities because physically healthy children are more able, highly focused and full of energies for appropriate attention towards constructive learning schedules.

Schools should plan children daily physical activities to last between 30-40 minutes or more and this should include moderate to vigorous activities.

Development of specific physical activities guidelines for school athletes and non athletes should be part of the school schedule, while doing all these, there must be appropriate supervision, control and monitoring by professionals and guides.

Health personnel should equally be on ground while planning all activities so that appropriate health test and remedies could be provided so as to achieve maximum performance and good result.

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